

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue I, January 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

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WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue I (January 2024)/ International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

Navigating Challenges and Advancements: Management Strategies for Enhancing Senior High Students' Research Experience in the Contemporary Educational Landscape

JOEMAR L. CAPINLAC, PhD.

Teacher III

Pines City National High School, CAR-BAGUIO CITY

Abstract

JOEMAR LANDAYAN CAPINLAC, PhD. January 2024. Navigating Challenges and Advancements: Management Strategies for Enhancing Senior High Students' Research Experience in the Contemporary Educational Landscape. Pines City National High School, Magsaysay Ave. Baguio City.

The study employed a qualitative methodology tailored to the case study. The aim of the study was to determine what challenges and strategies that the teacher faced when managing first semester introduction to research in Filipino subject to students in the modern era. Upon conducting an analysis of the study's data, it was found that teachers still face challenges when it comes to managing introduction to research subject in Filipino, including: First, students' disinterest in the topic of the research work, which can be attributed to a variety of factors such as limited vocabulary, difficulty in speaking Filipino, and an obsession with using various technologies. The second corresponds to not enough knowledge of Filipino orthography; the third is a gap in research work of the students.

However, the educators never give up trying to find new ways to infuse their everyday instruction with more creativity and meaning for every young person who aspires to receive a higher-quality education, nonetheless despite a variety of obstacles.

They remain proactive in diligence to incorporate strategies that will assist students' scholarly abilities. Based on the data analysis, five methods which teachers use in teaching introduction to research have been determined. These strategies include asking or raising questions during discussions, translating, modifying lessons, and working collaboratively.

As a result, refrain from allowing someone to cease learning new things and pushing oneself to become competent in the area of choice by attending seminars and workshops that will help young individuals who aspire obtain better education while honing their skills.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10559215

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